

D1.5. Data Management Plan - Update

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-centre clinical trial.

Deliverable D1.5 Description

A report detailing the data management plan (DMP) as an Output of Task 1.5. This document is the updated version of the DMP submitted in April 2024. The deliverable lists the management plan of data acquired through clinical studies B2, B3 and B4 which were not covered in the previous version.

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Didaskalou S, Jucevičius M, Maja S, Kaldoudi E, ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan - Update, Deliverable 1.5, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18087449>.

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
OS	Open Science
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GB	GigaByte
GDF	General Data Format for Biomedical Signals
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
PU	Public
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System

Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable is to describe in detail the Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP specifies how project outputs will be handled during and after the ThrombUS+ project. It identifies information about what datasets the ThrombUS+ consortium is aiming to acquire/generate and preserve, in which format and the data management lifecycle. Best practices in terms of metadata and archiving are described, ensuring that the datasets acquired or generated will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), in accordance with the Horizon Europe (HE) Open Science (OS).

As the DMP is a living document, this document constitutes the updated version of the initial DMP plan delivered in April 2024. The document covers changes with respect to the data collected by Clinical Study B2, as well as the management plan for the data collected via the additional Clinical Studies B3 and B4, which were not planned in the Grant Agreement. Respective updates will be published in Argos/Zenodo during the project.

1. Introduction

The initial data management plan (DMP) delivered in month M04 of the project, listed and comprehensively outlined the management plan of all primary types of data and datasets that will be generated within the ThrombUS+ project¹. Specifically, the management plan covered:

1. Data collected via the clinical studies planned in the project. The plan addressed data gathered from the clinical studies planned within the project, specifically Study A, Studies B1, B2, and Studies C1 and C2. These studies are integral to the project's research objectives and are designed to collect various types of data relevant to the ThrombUS+ prototype development and evaluation.
2. Technical and validation data collected during technical development, mainly as outcomes of experimental and validation work related to the research and innovation of the ThrombUS+ components.
3. Project deliverables. The management of data related to project deliverables was included in the plan. This encompasses all outputs and results that are expected to be produced as part of the project's deliverables, ensuring they are properly documented and managed.
4. Project publications and other dissemination and communication materials.
5. Literature used in the project. This involves the organization and documentation of all reference materials and literature that inform the project's research and development activities.

The present document serves as the first formal update to the initial Data Management Plan (DMP). It provides comprehensive progress reports on the project's outputs and outlines the refinements made to the data management strategy to reflect the project's current implementation status. While protocols for technical validation data, deliverables and publications remain largely consistent with the initial plan, this update details significant structural adaptations in the clinical studies protocols. Specifically, this report documents the transition of Clinical Study B2 into three distinct sub-studies (B2, B3 and B4) and confirms the project's continued adherence to FAIR principles through the utilization of the ThrombUS+ Zenodo community. The subsequent chapters provide a detailed analysis of these updates, organized by data type.

2. Management Plan Progress Report

2.1. Data collected via clinical studies

In accordance with the initial data management plan (DMP), data collected through Clinical Study A is intended for open access to facilitate reuse by the broader research community. The data may support further research and development in ultrasound image processing and analysis tasks. Furthermore, as outlined in the initial data management plan, the data collected will be utilized for training and public engagement through organised open-data challenges.

While data collection remains ongoing, a preliminary dataset of compression ultrasound videos, including their associated ground-truth labels, has already been published **to the ThrombUS+ Zenodo repository** (<https://zenodo.org/communities/thrombus>). The dataset currently consists of 2,919 compression ultrasound videos obtained from 742 enrolled patients.

To promote science awareness and maximize data reusability, two open-data challenges were launched on the Kaggle platform (Table 1). For these challenges, the dataset was partitioned into training and testing sets using an 80/20 ratio ensuring a robust framework for benchmarking ultrasound analysis algorithms (Table 2).

¹ Didaskalou S, Drosatos G, Kaldoudi E, ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan, Deliverable 1.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 30 April 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067925>

Table 1. ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Data Challenges.

Data challenges based on ThrombUS+ Study A data set #1 as published in Kaggle	
ThrombUS+ 1.1: DVT Diagnosis via Ultrasound Videos	https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/Thrombus_challenge_1_1
ThrombUS+ 1.2: Ultrasound-Based Vein Detection	https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/Thrombus_challenge_1_2

The deposition of the dataset into the Zenodo repository was performed in alignment with the **FAIR** data principles. This ensures that the research outputs of the ThrombUS+ project are maximized for scientific impact and transparency.

More specifically, the Zenodo repository has assigned a unique persistent **Digital Object Identifier** (DOI) to each dataset ensuring the datasets are Findable. This allows permanent linking and accurate citation in the future. In addition, the datasets are **Accessible** under open access terms (CC BY 4.0), ensuring that any researcher can retrieve and reuse the data using standard web protocols.

To support Interoperability, each dataset is accompanied by structured metadata. These metadata include, but are not limited to:

1. **Administrative Metadata:** project name (ThrombUS+), funding agency (European Commission), and contributors' details.
2. **Descriptive Metadata:** detailed description of the compression ultrasound videos, including ground-truth labels, such as anatomical site of the scanning area, compressibility of the veins, presence of thrombus, patient demographics and body composition measurements.
3. **Technical Metadata:** the file structure and the file format (DICOM, .csv). Ultrasound technical specifications metadata are included within the DICOM files, according to the DICOM standard.

The use of a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) maximizes Reusability, by allowing the data to be shared and adapted.

Table 2. ThrombUS+ Open Access Data Sets.

DOIs of the Open Access Datasets published at Zenodo	
ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Dataset #1 Compression Ultrasound Videos - Training Set	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17659414
ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Dataset #1 Compression Ultrasound Videos - Testing Set	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17664207

Upon the conclusion of the Clinical Study A, the current Zenodo depositions will be updated to include the comprehensive collection of all acquired ultrasound compression videos and their labels, including all related metadata. In accordance with the iterative nature of the data management plan reporting, this data management plan will be formally updated to reflect the final management plan, any refinement in metadata descriptors, and the long-term preservation strategy for the complete dataset.

In conclusion, the data management strategy for Clinical Studies A, B1, C2 and C2 remains fully consistent with the protocols of the initial DMP. The only deviations recorded during this period pertain to the restructuring of Study B2, as detailed in Chapter 3.

2.2. Technical and validation data

No deviations in comparison to the initial DMP were observed for the technical and validation data collected.

2.3. Project deliverables

All submitted project deliverables have been published as **Open Access** in the ThrombUS+ Zenodo repository under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (Table 3). To ensure these outputs are fully aligned with the FAIR principles, the following measures have been implemented:

1. **Findable and Accesibility:** Each deliverable has been assigned a unique Persistent Digital Identifier (DOI) and is indexed within the OpenAIRE infrastructure. Furthermore, these outputs are accessible within the dedicated EU Open Research Repository in Zenodo.
2. **Interoperability:** All depositions include standardized metadata, including contributor details, technical description, funding agency acknowledgments and versioning information.
3. **Reusability:** By the use of CC BY 4.0 license the consortium ensures that the project outputs can be widely shared and built upon by the research community, provided that the appropriate credit is given.

Table 3. Submitted deliverables enlisted with the full citations and their DOIs.

No.	Indicator	Title	Citation	DOI
1	D8.1	Project public website	Briola E, Project Public Website, Deliverable 8.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 29 March 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068009	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068009
2	D1.1	Management guide & collaboration infrastructure	Kaldoudi E, Management Guide and Collaboration Infrastructure, Publishable Summary of Deliverable 1.1, hrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 January 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085753	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085753
3	D10.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1		
4	D1.2	Quality assurance and risk management plan & activities - Part A	Didaskalou S, Kaldoudi E, Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan and Activities – Part A, Publishable Summary of Deliverable 1.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 29 March 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085959	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085959
5	D1.3	Innovation and IPR management plan and activities - Part A	Dionisio P, and the ThrombUS+ Consortium, Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan and Activities – Part 1, Publishable Summary of Deliverable 1.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11086031	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11086031
6	D8.2	Dissemination and communication plan and activities - Part A	Pavliidi K, Dissemination and communication plan and activities - Part A, Deliverable 8.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11091334	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11091334

7	D9.1	Regulatory compliance monitoring plan and activities - Part A	Prinz T, Narten Z, Wenner H, Schlötelburg C, Regulatory compliance monitoring plan and activities, Part A, Deliverable 9.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 27 March 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11091568	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11091568
8	D1.4	Data management plan	Didaskalou S, Drosatos G, Kaldoudi E, ThrombUS+ Data Management Plan, Deliverable 1.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 30 April 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067925	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067925
9	D7.1	Clinical studies initiation package - Study A	Drougka I, Clinical studies initiation package - Study A, Deliverable 7.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 May 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371924	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371924
10	D2.1	Patient-centric cases and requirements definition	Segal LJ, Puppo F, Folkvord F, Patient-centric cases and requirements definition, Deliverable 2.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 28 June 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12554621	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12554621
11	D2.2	Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics strategy and guidelines	Prinz T, Narten Z, Wenner H, Didaskalou S, and Schlötelburg C, Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics strategy and guidelines, Deliverable 2.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 16 July 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12726793	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12726793
12	D2.3	Technical and functional requirements	Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Prinz T, Lukoševičius A, Jurkonis R, Eitminavičius R, Didaskalou S, Vehkaoja A, Ahola R, Slabov A, Jegelevičius D, Balling S, Moutafidou A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A. Technical and functional requirements, Deliverable 2.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 October 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671
13	D2.4	Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable	Cesana J, Annunziata S, Moltani LA, Didaskalou S, Jurkonis R, Marozas V, Lukoševičius A, Schubert F, Balling S, Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable, Deliverable 2.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 December 2024. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352778	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352778
14	D3.1	Ultrasound transducer array prototypes based on bulk technology (2 linear and 2 H shaped)	Legros M, Pousset N, Toffessi Siewe S, Boulay S, Voisin D, Raybaud G, Deliverable 3.1, Ultrasound Transducer Array Prototypes: Composite PZT technology, Deliverable 3.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 2 January 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500724	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500724

15	D3.2	Ultrasound transducer prototypes based on MEMS (2 prototypes)	Völz U., Kircher M., Lange N., Ultrasound Transducer Prototypes: MEMS Technology, Deliverable 3.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 02 January 2025, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540400	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540400
16	D3.3	Precise, silent tissue compression actuator prototypes (2 prototypes)	R. Eitminavičius, R. Jurkonis, V. Marozas, S. Daukantas, A. Sakalauskas, A. Slabov, Precise Tissue Compression Actuator, Deliverable D3.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 04 January 2025, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540479	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540479
17	D4.1	Sensors and processing software for electrical impedance plethysmography DVT detection (2 sets)	Verho J, Ahola R, Maja S, Vehkaoja A. Sensors and processing software for electrical impedance plethysmography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540486	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540486
18	D4.2	Sensors and processing software for light reflection rheography DVT detection (2 sets)	Balling S, Querengässer J, Schubert F, Sensors and processing software for light reflection rheography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540537	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540537
19	D4.3	Sensors and processing software for lower limb activity pattern recognition (2 sets)	Jucevičius M, Marozas V, Daukantas S, Lukoševičius A. Sensors and processing software for lower limb activity pattern recognition (2 sets), Deliverable 4.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540539	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540539
20	D7.2	Midterm clinical studies recruitment reports	Drougka I, Didaskalou S, Drosatos G, Kaldoudi E, Midterm clinical studies recruitment Reports, Deliverable 7.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 15 January 2025, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371924	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371924
21	D7.3	Clinical studies initiation package - Studies B1 and B2	Drougka I, Didaskalou S, Narten SZ, Novikov D, Vehkaoja A, Jucevicius M, Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Clinical studies initiation package - Studies B, Deliverable 7.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 14 February 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864861	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864861
22	D6.1	Integrated product technical specifications	Marozas V, Portokallidis N, Jurkonis R, Jucevičius M, Eitminavičius R, Lukoševičius A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A, Sonda A, Moutafidou A, Cesana J, Moustakidis P, Lange N, Balling S, Querengässer J, Legros M, Novikov D, Maja S, Prinz T, Kaldoudi E. Product Design Specifications, Deliverable 6.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930624

			Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 28 February 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930624	
23	D3.4	Ultrasound transducer control and image formation	Sakalauskas A, Prysiazniuk A, Novikov D, Ultrasound Transducer Control and Image Formation, Deliverable D3.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15113600	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15113600
24	D7.4	Report on status of posting of clinical studies - Study A	Didaskalou S, N Portokallidis, Drougka I, Kaldoudi E, Report on Status of Posting of Results – Study A, Deliverable 7.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 25 November 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17641971	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17641971
25	D4.4	Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors (2 prototypes)	Cesana J, Annunziata S, LA Moltani LA. Prototypes of wearable strap and sock with sensors (2 prototypes), Deliverable 4.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 May 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15310384	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15310384
26	D6.2	Testing methodology and test plan	Rapolis A., Jucevičius M., Daukantas S., Lukoševičius A., Eitminavičius R., Jurkonis R., Balling S., Querengässer J., Maja S., Vehkaoja A., Prinz T., Portokallidis N., Didaskalou S., Marozas V., Kaldoudi E., Testing methodology and test plan, Deliverable D6.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 30 June 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15769783	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15769783
27	D3.5	Report on testing of arrays, pump and image formation electronics for image quality and required enhancements	Sakalauskas A, Novikov D, Jurkonis R. Report on testing of arrays, pump and image formation electronics for image quality and required enhancements, Deliverable D3.5, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 5 August 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16415191	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16415191
28	D4.5	Report on testing of wearable and sensors for signal quality and required enhancements	Jucevicius M, Cessana J, Huopalainen M, Balling S, Daukantas S, Eitminavičius R, Querengaeser J, Maja S, Ahola R, Rapolis A, Didaskalou S, Lukoševičius A, Vehkaoja A, Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Testing, signal quality and performance enhancement of the wearable sensor network, Deliverable 4.5, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 02 August 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16656680	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16656680
29	D10.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	Sardeli C., ThrombUS+ Ethics Appraisal Report #1, Deliverable D10.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 23 December 2024, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14510676	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14510676

30	D10.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	Sardeli C., ThrombUS+ Ethics Appraisal Report #2, Deliverable D10.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 18 December 2025. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17963777 , Publishable Summary.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17963777
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2.4. Project publications and other dissemination and communication materials

There has been no deviation from the initial data management plan (DMP) regarding the handling of scientific publication and communication materials. The consortium remains committed to the following Open Science practices:

1. **Open Access Compliance:** All scientific publication outputs are provided under Open Access Terms. In cases where the publisher's terms do not support immediate open access, the Author Acceptor Manuscript or a pre-print version is deposited in both the ThrombUS+ website (<https://thrombus.eu/index.php/innovation/publications>) and the ThrombUS+ Zenodo community to ensure public availability.
2. **Communication Materials:** All dissemination and communication materials (e.g. posters, presentations and newsletters) are likewise shared via the project's website and Zenodo community.
3. **Persistent Identification:** As with the clinical data and deliverables, all published papers and materials are assigned a unique identifier (DOI). This ensures persistent linking with the contributors, the ThrombUS+ project, the funding agency and their metadata.

2.5. Literature used in the project

There has been no deviation from the initial management plan regarding literature management. To ensure efficient collaboration and transparency, consortium members utilize the Zotero open-access platform for managing and maintaining all literature to the project.

3. Data Management Plan Updates

With respect to the initial management plan (DMP), only deviations to the management plan of data collected via the Clinical Study B2 are presented. According to Description of Action (DoA) Clinical Study B2 was initially planned to collect multi-sensor data from the underdevelopment ThrombUS+ prototype sensor network from healthy volunteers. Therefore, the initial data management plan regarding Clinical Study B2, refers to multi-sensor data, including physiological signals, lower limb activity data, light reflection rheography measurements and electrical impedance plethysmography data. However, during protocol development, it was deemed more efficient to amend the initial plan and break Clinical Study B2, into three individual studies. Consequently, this data management plan is an update to the initial data management plan for Clinical Study B2 also covering data management of studies B3 and B4. The scope of these new studies is summarized below:

1. **Clinical Study B2:** A single-centre observational cohort study to collect lower limb activity measurements from healthy volunteers during physiotherapy exercises using commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) and camera sensors to create a training data set for research purposes, including signal processing and analysis and AI model training.
2. **Clinical Study B3:** A single-center observational cohort study to collect lower limb activity measurements from healthy volunteers during physiotherapy exercises using the inertial measurement unit (IMU) system developed in the ThrombUS+ and commercial fixed position

cameras with the aim of testing and optimizing IMU performance and sensor fusion algorithms for human motion tracking.

3. **Clinical Study B4:** Pilot phase clinical investigation to collect electrical impedance plethysmography data set from healthy volunteers and DVT patients using ThrombUS+ prototype device developed during the project and commercial equivalent device as reference.

The complete DMP for each of the above-mentioned dataset follows the **Argos/HE** template and are provided in the Annex of this deliverable. The complete updated Data Management Plan, including Clinical Studies A, B1, B2, B3, C1 and C2 are available via the **Argos/Zenodo** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16322665>). Table 4 summarizes the available versions of ThrombUS+ Data Management Plans, along their respective DOIs.

Table 4. Versions of ThrombUS+ Data Management Plans

Version 0	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068584
Version 1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16322666
Version 2 (this version)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18088005

Annex: Updated DMPs for ThrombUS+ Datasets of Studies B2, B3 and B4

The following data management plans follow the Horizon Europe DMP template as implemented in the Argos DMP tool.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B2 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B2 Dataset: Lower limb activity measurements collected via wearable sensors and video cameras from normal volunteers.
Description:	Lower limb activity measurements via wearable inertial measurement units (IMUs) and video cameras with a set of labels for each measurement including participants demographics, collected from 60 healthy volunteers
Tags:	Deep Vein Thrombosis, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), Physiotherapy Exercises, Lower Limb Activity Data
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data
Type of data:	Digital
New or re-using the data	New
Type of the dataset:	Observational. Lower limb activity data from healthy volunteers while performing common physiotherapy exercises in lying, sitting and standing positions.
Format of the data:	<p>Data collected will comprise of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) (.csv, .txt). – Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4). – Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference). <p>Processed data sets will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) (.csv, .txt). – Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4). – Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference) (.csv, .txt). <p>Signal labelling data in JSON format.</p>
Expected size:	Less than 15GB
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To develop a product. Training AI models.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from healthy volunteers in Democritus University of Thrace and the ATHENA RC.
Data utility:	Researchers.

		<p>Research communities.</p> <p>Industry.</p>
2.	Links between outputs	
	Does the described output support any scientific publication?	<p>Not at the moment.</p> <p>The data is expected to support publication in the course of the project</p>
	Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
	Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to train AI models developed in the ThrombUS+ project.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite's Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	<p>DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf.</p> <p>SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/.</p> <p>ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/.</p>
	Are the metadata searchable?	<p>Yes.</p> <p>Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.</p>
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep Vein Thrombosis, Lower Limb Activity Data, Physiotherapy Exercises, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs).
	Are metadata harvestable?	<p>Yes .</p> <p>Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.</p>
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ .
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	<p>Yes.</p> <p>Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.</p>

	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ .

		ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set
5.	Security	
	What security measures are followed?	None.
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A.
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.

6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	No.
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7.	Other Issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No.

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B3 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B3 Dataset: Lower limb activity measurements collected via prototype wearable sensors and video cameras from normal volunteers.
Description:	Lower limb activity measurements via prototype inertial measurement unit (IMU) based sensors and video cameras with a set of labels for each measurement including participants demographics, collected from 10 healthy volunteers.
Tags:	Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT), Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs), Physiotherapy Exercises, Limb Position, Limb Orientation, Lower Limb Activity Data
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data
Type of data:	Digital
New or re-using the data	New
Type of the dataset:	Reference or canonical. Lower limb activity data from prototype IMU-based system, with video reference, from healthy volunteers while performing common physiotherapy exercises in lying, sitting and standing positions.
Format of the data:	<p>Data collected will comprise of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via prototype inertial measurement units (IMU) based system (.csv, .txt, .gdf). Data will include time (ms), acceleration (m/s^2), angular velocity (rad/s) and quaternions (w, x, y and z). – Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4). – Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference). <p>Processed data sets will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Anonymized lower limb activity signals measured via custom inertial measurement units (IMU) based system (.csv, .txt, .gdf). Data will include time (ms), acceleration (m/s^2), angular velocity (rad/s) and quaternions (w, x, y and z). – Anonymized video recording of lower limb activity from two separate views (.mp4). – Anonymized demographics and biometrics (sex, age, race, height, weight, thigh circumference) (.csv, .txt). <p>Signal labelling data in JSON format.</p>
Expected size:	Less than 5GB
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To obtain information. To make informed decisions. To develop a product. To improve a product. To improve and validate limb segment orientation estimation algorithms.

	Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from healthy volunteers in Democritus University of Thrace and ATHENA RC.
	Data utility:	Researchers. Research communities. Industry.
2.	Links between outputs	
	Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Not at the moment. The data is expected to support publication in the course of the project
	Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	An availability statement will be provided.
	Does the described output use or support any software?	Data will be used to improve and validate limb segment orientation estimation firmware of the ThrombUS+ lower limb activity device prototype.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers: DOI
	Will metadata be available?	DataCite's Metadata Schema supported by Zenodo.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/ .
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes. Metadata are indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and are also automatically linked to the OpenAIRE graph.
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT), Lower Limb Activity Data, Physiotherapy Exercises, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs).
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes. Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ .

	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	Yes. Zenodo is developed by CERN and the OpenAIRE organization under EU funding and is part of the EOSC EU initiative.
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	Yes. DOI.
	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	Yes
	Does the repository support versioning?	Yes. Zenodo supports versioning.
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	To be decided.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Open.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	Zenodo
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	Zenodo's REST API
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	Internet connection and a browser.
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	Yes, ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	Shared under restrictions to be defined by ThrombUS+ General Assembly.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Indefinitely.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CC0).
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes. DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes.
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf .

		SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records, https://www.snomed.org/ . ICD, International Classification of Diseases, https://icd.who.int/en/
	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	DataCite Schema for data description, https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCite-MetadadataKernel_v4.0.pdf . Proprietary schema for JSON files included in data set, using controlled vocabularies as possible.
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate, such as general medical data format (.gdf) for recording and storing the data
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards , controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	Medical controlled vocabularies are mapped and crosslinked via UMLS.
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	To be decided.
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files.
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No.
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	To be decided.
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes. The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved via Ethics Committees. The protocol ID will be provided.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Set up of scientific and technical committee. Use of tools for automatic checks. Data conform to format specification.
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	Part of the cost for WP7 and WP8 of ThrombUS+ project.
	How will this cost be covered?	ThrombUS+ project
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Eleni Kaldoudi, ThrombUS+ Coordinator Role: High level management of the data set Stelios Didaskalou, ThrombUS+ Project Manager Role: Technical management of the data set Mantas Jucevičius, ThrombUS+ Project Researcher Role: Technical management of the data set

5. Security	
What security measures are followed?	None.
What conditions do the security measures meet?	N/A.
How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Via publication in Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	Data will be collected via a clinical study protocol approved by relevant ethics committees and after informed consent.
Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	No.
Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	No.
What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	Anonymising data where necessary. Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms. Data accompanied by informed consent statements.
7. Other issues	
Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No

ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B4 Dataset	
Title of the dataset:	ThrombUS+ Clinical Study B4 Dataset: Physiological signals and electrical impedance plethysmography measurements collected from thrombolytic DVT patients and healthy volunteers
Description:	Electrical impedance plethysmography and ECG measurements with associated labels for each set of measurements, including participant demographics, collected from 20 patients during catheter-directed thrombolysis and 20 healthy volunteers.
Tags:	Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT), Impedance Plethysmography, Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP), Lower Limb, Physiological Signals
1.	Data Summary
Kind of research output:	Research Data
Type of data:	Digital
New or re-using the data	New
Type of the dataset:	Observational Experimental Derived or Compiled Electrical impedance plethysmography signals, electrical impedance plethysmography parameters, ECG signals, patient demographics and biometrics
Format of the data:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Electrical impedance plethysmography signals (csv, .mat files) – Electrical impedance plethysmography parameters (PDF) – ECG signals (ASCII file). – Patient demographics and biometrics in a Word document (.docx)
Expected size:	< 10 GB
Reason for collecting/generating/ re-using the data:	To obtain information. To develop a product. Other. Training AI models.
Origin/ provenance of the data:	Data collected from 20 thrombolytic DVT patients and 20 healthy volunteers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Data from healthy volunteers collected in Health and Assistive Technology Laboratory at Tampere University. – Data from DVT patients in Tampere University Hospital.
Data utility:	Researchers
2.	Links between outputs
Does the described output support any scientific publication?	Yes One manuscript has been submitted. Other manuscripts are in preparation.

	Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	No
	Does the described output use or support any software?	Yes The dataset is used for developing signal processing and machine learning algorithms for ThrombUS+ EIM software. The software is under development.
3.	FAIR practices	
3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
	What type of Persistent Identifier will be used?	Data identifiers. DOI (for metadata only).
	Will metadata be available?	Yes Will be available via Zenodo and follows the DataCite's Metadata Schema.
	Type(s) of metadata:	Descriptive. Administrative.
	Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	Yes DataCite Schema for data description (https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCiteMetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf) SNOMED-CT standardized, international, multilingual core set of clinical healthcare terminology that can be used in electronic health records (https://www.snomed.org/) ICD, International Classification of Diseases (https://icd.who.int/en/).
	Are the metadata searchable?	Yes DataCite Metadata Schema
	Keywords provided in the metadata:	Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT). Electrical Impedance Plethysmography (EIP). Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP). Lower Limb
	Are metadata harvestable?	Yes Via Zenodo, metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.
3.2	Making data and other outputs openly accessible	
3.2.1	Repository	
	In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	None (Dataset stored locally or internal network drive)
	Is the selected repository a trusted source?	N/A
	Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited.	N/A
	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	N/A

	Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?	N/A
	Does the repository support versioning?	N/A
3.2.2	Data	
	What is the described dataset / output title?	Impedance and venous occlusion plethysmography signals during catheter-directed thrombolysis for the assessment deep vein thrombosis.
	How is the dataset / output shared?	Closed The study's privacy policy does not allow publication or sharing of the data. Patient data is difficult to anonymize due to the small number of potential participants. Since patient data cannot be published, the entire dataset will keep closed.
	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	N/A
	Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.	N/A
	Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.	N/A
	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?	No
	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends	During the project: Access is restricted to research group members. After the project ends (or a maximum of 10 years after the study): The dataset will be anonymized and archived in the Tampere University. Access will remain restricted due to the sensitive nature of the dataset.
	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	Pseudonymized data is stored in electronic form for a maximum of 10 years. After that the data is anonymized and archived in Tampere University.
3.2.3	Metadata	
	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?	Yes
	Under which license will metadata be provided?	Creative Commons Zero (CCO)
	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?	Yes DataCite provides relevant fields.
	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	Yes
3.3	Making data and other outputs interoperable	
	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	Yes DataCite Schema for data description: https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/doc/DataCiteMetadataKernel_v4.0.pdf

	If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?	N/A
	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	Yes DataCite's Metadata Schema
	What is the methodology followed?	Using common standards and format where appropriate.
	What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?	Widely used medical standards, controlled vocabularies, and terminologies.
	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	No
3.4	Increasing data and other outputs re-use	
	What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?	None (dataset is for internal use only, not publicly licensed)
	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?	Readme files Data cleaning Variable definitions Units of measurements Negative results sharing
	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	No
	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?	No
	Is provenance well documented?	Yes The data will be collected via clinical study protocol approved by local by the local ethical review board of the Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa and the national competent authority of Finland, Fimea.
	What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?	Use of tools for automatic checks Data conform to format specification Other: Logs of investigational devices and data collection activities, clinical investigation monitoring
4.	Allocation of resources	
	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	None
	How will this cost be covered?	N/A
	Define who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output.	Antti Vehkaoja (ORCID: 0000-0003-3721-3467) Professor, Leader of Sensor Technology and Biomeasurements Group (Tampere University), GA member in the ThrombUS+ project Role: High level management of the dataset Sami Maja (ORCID: 0009-0009-9052-3780) Researcher in Sensor Technology and Biomeasurements Group (Tampere University), project team member in the ThrombUS+ project Role: Technical management of the dataset
5.	Security	

	What security measures are followed?	<p>Passwords (with username)</p> <p>Other: Data are pseudonymized and thus collected without directly identifying information.</p>
	What conditions do the security measures meet?	<p>Data access: Access are restricted to research group members.</p> <p>Data storage: The data are stored in pseudonymized form on the researcher's computers or internal network drivers, protected with a username and password.</p> <p>Data sharing: The data are not shared.</p> <p>Data recovery: Data are stored on several researcher' computers and internal network drive, which enables backup.</p>
	How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?	Pseudonymized data is stored in electronic form for a maximum of 10 years. After that, the data will be anonymised and archived in Tampere University.
6.	Ethical aspects	
	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?	<p>Yes</p> <p>Data sharing restricted by the Data Protection Act (Tietosuojalaki 1050/2018) of Finland and GDPR. The study's privacy policy also restricts data sharing. The study for data collection has been approved by the local ethical review board of the Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa and the national competent authority of Finland, Fimea.</p>
	Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?	Yes
	Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?	Yes
	What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?	<p>Anonymising data where necessary</p> <p>Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms</p> <p>Privacy policies</p> <p>National laws</p>
7.	Other issues	
	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	No